

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case and a Math Function $S = \sum_i p(e_i) f(p(e_i))$ Such That $dE/dT = TdS/dT$

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The notion of maximizing the number of physical arrangements of N molecules with $n(e_i)$ having energy e_i such that the total energy is E , leads to the mathematical maximization of: $\ln(N! / \sum_i n(e_i)!) - b \sum_i e_i n(e_i)$, where $n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$. One only obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ if one uses Stirling's approximation, $\ln(n!) = n \ln(n)$. Nevertheless, the maximization of arrangements is based on physical reality.

In (1), it is argued that one may obtain a distribution (including the Maxwell-Boltzmann one) from the first law of thermodynamics, without any notion of maximization, but a priori knowledge of the first law of thermodynamics.

Here we consider $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ and ask if one may find a mathematical function: $S = -\sum_i p(e_i) f(p(e_i))$ such that: $dE_{ave} = T dS$. This is a simplified form of the first law of thermodynamics, i.e. one with no work, but we consider the approach as a math based one. In other words, one could derive the first law of thermodynamics for cases of no work in such a manner. We show that this may be done if one considers $p(e_i) = C(T) p_1(e_i/T)$. In other words, there exists an unnormalized function $p_1(e_i/T)$ which must contain an argument with no units as probability is simply a number. We then show that a particular math solution allows for $S = -\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ such that $dE - TdS = 0$. This approach uses neither maximization nor knowledge of the first law of thermodynamics. It is simply a math approach which allows for the form $dE = TdS$ with a specific math form for S as a function of $p(e_i)$ and $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$. Given the math result, one might suggest that it is a microscopic representation of the first law of thermodynamics for no work, or given knowledge of $p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T)$ from MaxEnt or reaction balance, one might introduce $dE = TdS$ as an equation describing changes due to heat (not work). In other words, MaxEnt or reaction balance leads to this simplified form of the first law of thermodynamics.

MaxEnt

A traditional approach to finding the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is based on a physical scenario, i.e. maximizing the number of distinct arrangements of a total energy E distributed among N particles. In such a case, one maximizes:

$$\ln(N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!) - b \sum_i e_i n(e_i) \quad ((1)) \text{ where } n(e_i) = N p(e_i)$$

Here b is a Lagrange multiplier.

One only obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution if one uses Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(n!) = n \ln(n) \quad ((2))$$

Finding a Distribution from the First Law of Thermodynamics

In (1), it is argued that one may find a distribution directly from the first law of thermodynamics:

$$dE - TdS - \sum_i A_i b_i = 0 \quad ((3))$$

We wish to ask the question, Is it possible to find a function $S(p(e_i))$ such that:

$$dE - T dS = 0 \quad ((4)) ?$$

This goal does not involve MaxEnt, nor does it involve a priori knowledge of the first law of thermodynamics, but should lead to a specific form of $S(p(e_i))$ and a specific distribution $p(e_i)$.

Postulating the Form $dE - TdS = 0$ form $S(p(e_i))$

We suggest that one may postulate the math form $S(p(e_i/T))$ such that

$$dE - TdS = 0 \text{ leads to a solution for } S \text{ and } p(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

The question then becomes: Why would one wish to do this?

We argue that unnormalized probability should be a function of a dimensionless variable:

$$e_i/T \quad ((6))$$

This unnormalized probability must then be normalized, i.e.

$$p(e_i) = C(T) p_1(e_i/T) \quad ((7))$$

The main point we make is that there should exist a function f which is the inverse of p_1 which may extract e_i/T from p_1 as this is the key variable in:

$$E_{ave} = \sum_i p(e_i) e_i \quad ((8))$$

We first consider:

$$S = \sum_i p(e_i) f(p(e_i)) \text{ where } p(e_i) \text{ is the normalized probability } ((9))$$

We suggest that one may change $p(e) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, by changing T , i.e. by doing no work, but by allowing heat to enter the system.

Then:

$$dE = \sum_i dp(e_i) e_i \text{ such that } \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((10))$$

If ((4)) is to hold, one must consider:

$$dS = \sum_i dp(e_i) f(p(e_i)) + \sum_i dp(e_i) p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) \quad ((11))$$

Note: $p(e_i)$ in ((11)) is the normalized probability.

If one wishes to make use of $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$, one might make the consideration:

$$p(e_i) df/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{so that the last term on the RHS of ((11)) is 0} \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{This leads to } f(p(e_i)) = \ln(p(e_i)) = \ln(C(T)) + \ln(p_1(e_i/T)) \quad ((13))$$

If one considers the first term on the RHS of ((11)), then:

$$\ln(C(T)) \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad \text{and } \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p_1(e_i)) \text{ should equal } \sum_i p(e_i) (-e_i/T). \quad ((14))$$

$$\text{This then suggests that: } S = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ with } p(e_i) = C(T) \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((15))$$

These are purely mathematical arguments, which do not need to be manifested in nature. One may, however, note that $dE = TdS$ actually appears in physics theory (and nature) as the first law of thermodynamics, with no work terms. As a result, the above may be a microscopic manifestation of this first law.

Furthermore, $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ may be obtained through MaxEnt or reaction balance and so we argue that if one knew of the MB distribution based on these different methods and did not know the first law of thermodynamics, one would arrive at its form for energy changes based on heat and not work.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution from a MaxEnt approach or reaction balance. In (1), it is argued that one may start with the first law of thermodynamics and $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ and obtain probability distributions. Here we consider the following strictly math problem. We write $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$ and ask: Does there exist a math function $S(p(e_i)) = \sum_i p(e_i) f(p(e_i))$ such that $dE = T dS$? We show that one may construct such a function using $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ such that $S = - \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ and $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$. We do not consider MaxEnt or have any a priori knowledge of the first law of thermodynamics. Given that this result is found, one may then compare it to the first law of thermodynamics and suggest that it is a possible microscopic representation of entropy in that law. Alternatively, given that $p(e_i) = C(T)\exp(-e_i/T)$ from MaxEnt or reaction balance, one may propose that the distribution found is linked with the relation $dE = TdS$ for energy changes due to a temperature change, i.e. find the simplified form of the first law of thermodynamics.

References

1. Plastino, A. and Curado, E.M. Generating Statistical Distributions without Maximizing the Entropy (2005) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/cond-mat/0509070>